

KNOWLEDGE OF NURSES ON NEONATAL SEPSIS: A TERTIARY TEACHING HOSPITAL-BASED STUDY

Mahvish Qazi

Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics²

Syed Muneeb Mohammed

*Department of Pediatrics
SKIMS Medical College and Hospital
Srinagar, Jammu and Kashmir, India, 190018*

Najmus Saqib✉

*Department of Pediatrics
Government Medical College, Doda
Jammu and Kashmir, India, 182202
shstar321@gmail.com*

Zahoor Hussain Daraz¹

Niraj Kumar¹

*¹Department of Pediatrics²
²Government Medical College, Jammu
Jammu and Kashmir, India, 180001*

✉ Corresponding author

Abstract

Neonatal sepsis is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in hospitalized newborns and premature infants. Therefore, knowledge of essential newborn Care (ENC) is important for a newborn's survival, growth and development.

The aim of this study was to assess the knowledge of nurses regarding essential newborn care in our Special Care Neonatal Unit (SCNU).

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted between 1st September 2021 and 30th November 2021 among the nurses working in SNCU of Government Medical College and Hospital (GMC), Doda, Jammu and Kashmir, India. Data were collected using a pre-tested questionnaire by purposive sample. Collected data were checked, and coding was done and analyzed using SPSS 20 software.

Results: 72.0 % of nurses were of the age group of 21–30 years. The majority (74 %) were females, 78 % had completed B Sc Nursing, and 66 % had experience of 2 to 4 years. Most of the nurses had good knowledge about ENC, about basic equipment's used in SNCU, and about advanced equipment's or procedures had less knowledge. All nurses answered bacteria correctly as a causative organism of neonatal sepsis.

Conclusions: Most of the nurses working in the SCNU of GMC Doda had good knowledge regarding ENC. The knowledge appeared irrespective of their age, gender, religion, educational status, working place and special courses/training in neonatology.

Keywords: Knowledge, Essential newborn Care, SCNU, Neonatal sepsis.

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1. Introduction

Neonatal sepsis is a clinical syndrome identified by systemic signs of infection and bacteremia in the neonatal phase [1]. Sepsis is not only an infection but also includes a spectrum of symptoms of systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) to septic shock. It may be divided into early onset sepsis {EONS} (presenting in the first 72 hours of life) and late-onset sepsis {LONS} (presenting after the first 72 hours of life). LONS is related to neonatal factors and generally affects newborns hospitalized in Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs), which means

that it is acquired from the hospital environment [2]. LONS is strongly associated with the procedures and contamination present in the NICUs. An infection could be bacterial, viral, fungal, or rickettsial.

Globally, 2.4 million children died in the first month of life in 2019 – approximately 6,700 neonatal death every day – with about a third of all neonatal death occurring within the first day after birth and close to three-quarters occurring within the first week of life [3]. Ninety per cent of these deaths take place in developing countries [4]. Infections, birth asphyxia, prematurity and low birth weight are major causes of death within this period [5]. Newborn complications resulting from hypothermia, infection and birth asphyxia that occur within the first seven days following birth contribute to the highest burden of morbidity and mortality [6].

ENC is designed to improve the health of newborns through a minimum set of interactions that should be made available for all births. ENC is based on simple principles of prevention of infection, thermal protection, resuscitation of the newborn with asphyxia, early and exclusive breastfeeding, care of low birthweight babies and identification and appropriate referral of sick neonates. Healthcare professionals provided at the time of birth are critical in helping to prevent complications and ensure survival [7]. ENC also requires professional skills along with communication-related to theoretical and practical knowledge. Being the primary contact personnel, knowledge regarding ENC could directly impact neonatal morbidity and mortality. Nurses are the key health workers in the newborn healthcare system.

The aim of the research was to assess the knowledge of nurses regarding essential newborn care in our setup.

2. Material and methods

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted between 1st September 2021 and 30th November 2021 among the nurses working in SNCU of Government Medical College and Hospital, Doda, Jammu and Kashmir, India. The inclusion criteria set for sample selection were nurses working in the SNCU of Government Medical College and Hospital, Doda, with full-time employment. A total of 50 nurses were recruited for the study. Consent was taken from the nurses. The study's general objective was to assess the nurse's knowledge of ENC. Several strategies were utilized to protect the rights of nurses who agreed to participate in this study. First, oral verbal consent from the nurses was taken before administering the questionnaire. The nurses were explained the purpose of the study and that they had the right to refuse to participate. Also, the voluntary nature of participation as well as confidentiality was stressed. Furthermore, the nurses were told they could refrain from answering any questions and leave the study at any time. The anonymity of the nurses was maintained at all times, and confidentiality of the obtained data was guaranteed that they.

A self-administered pre-tested semi-structured questionnaire was developed by researchers reviewing the related literature and consulting with the related experts. There were altogether twenty-eight questions set on the basis of the ENC component. The questionnaire was organized into two parts; sociodemographic characteristics and nurses' knowledge regarding ENC. Knowledge was graded as satisfactory or not satisfactory. When the participant gave the right answer, it was graded as satisfactory if wrong, then not satisfactory.

Statistical analysis: The data of the present study were prepared, organized and entered into the computer through the application of the statistical package for social science version 20, which consists of the following:

- a. Descriptive data analysis
- b. Inferential data analysis.

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee title GMC Doda/IEC/2021/08 date 17/08/21 and the protocol number 090721-27. Researchers collected data from nurses using a structured questionnaire through face-to-face interview. Data quality control was checked for the completeness of the questionnaire after receiving it from the participants.

3. Results

Table 1 shows that among 50 nurses who participated in the study, more than half, 36 (72.0 %) nurses were 21–30 years old. In addition, the majority 37 (74 %), were females, 26 (52 %) belonged to the Hindu religion, 27 (54 %) were unmarried, 39 (78 %) had completed B Sc Nursing, 33 (66 %) had experience of 2 to 4 years, and most of them 41 (82 %) have not done any specialized course in neonatology.

Table 1
Sociodemographic characteristics of nurses

Demographic characteristic	Number (50)	Percentage
Age (years)		
≤20	4	8 %
21–30	36	72 %
31–40	7	14 %
>40	3	6 %
Gender		
Male	13	26 %
Female	37	74 %
Religion		
Islam	24	48 %
Hinduism	26	52 %
Marital status		
Married	23	46 %
Unmarried	27	54 %
Educational status		
Diploma	11	22 %
B Sc Nursing	39	78 %
Years of experience		
1–2 years	9	18 %
2–4 years	33	66 %
More than 4 years	8	16 %
Attending special courses/training in neonatology		
Yes	9	18 %
No	41	82 %

Most of the nurses had good knowledge of ENC, as shown in **Table 2**. All nurses know about timely vaccination. The most frequent neonatal sepsis prevention strategies mainly adopted by the respondents included hand washing (96 %), equipment sterilization (96.0 %), regular changing of bed sheets (92 %), umbilical cord care (94.0 %), maternal health education (90 %), minimization of invasive procedures (92 %), initiation of breastfeeding (98 %) and cutting of nails (76 %) respectively.

Table 3 shows that all nurses, 50 (100 %), knew bacteria as causative organisms of neonatal sepsis, but only 37 (74 %) knew about viruses, and 24 (48 %) came up with fungi as causative organisms.

Out of 50 nurses working in SNCU, most of the nurses had good knowledge about basic equipment used in SNCU viz Ambu bags and masks (92 %), Suction machine (84 %), Endotracheal tubes of different sizes (94 %), Oxygen source (96 %), Pulse oximetry (92 %) whereas about advance equipment's or procedures had less knowledge viz Central line kit (24 %), Arterial line kit (8 %), Mechanical ventilators (4 %) etc. (**Table 4**).

Of the nurses, 46 % identified pre-labour rupture of membranes as a risk factor, and 54 % identified intrapartum maternal pyrexia. Majority of them (82 %) knew prematurity was a risk factor. Even though intrapartum minimum handling is very important in preventing early-onset neonatal sepsis, only 32 % identified that as a risk factor. More importantly, 86 % came up with poor hand hygiene as a risk factor for neonatal sepsis (**Table 5**).

Table 2
Distribution of Level of Knowledge among nurses about Essential Newborn Care

Variables	Frequency distribution	
	Correct	Incorrect
Questions on Essential Newborn Care		
Meaning of Essential Newborn Care	48 (96 %)	2 (4 %)
Neonatal sepsis refers to sepsis in a child	47 (94 %)	3 (6 %)
Causes		
Maternal malnutrition	46 (92 %)	4 (8 %)
Evil spirit	3 (6 %)	47 (94 %)
Delivery room environment	49 (98 %)	1 (2 %)
Neonatal sepsis generally manifests as	42 (84 %)	8 (16 %)
Premature infants are at greater risk of sepsis if born earlier than	40 (80 %)	10 (20 %)
Clinical features of neonatal sepsis frequently involve changes to	43 (86 %)	7 (14 %)
In a child with suspected sepsis, the temperature is a red flag if it is	45 (90 %)	5 (10 %)
About resuscitation	41 (82 %)	9 (18 %)
Consequences of missing sepsis	38 (76 %)	12 (24 %)
Measure for warming the baby	49 (98 %)	1 (2 %)
Umbilical cord care	47 (94 %)	3 (6 %)
Initiation of breastfeeding	49 (98 %)	1 (2 %)
Advice if breast milk does not come	48 (96 %)	2 (4 %)
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding	45 (90 %)	5 (10 %)
Eye care	46 (92 %)	4 (8 %)
Time of Vaccination	50 (100 %)	0 (0 %)
Low birthweight baby	43 (86 %)	7 (14 %)
The stabilizing temperature of low birthweight baby	45 (90 %)	5 (10 %)
Extra care to low birthweight baby	37 (74 %)	13 (26 %)
Bed sheets should be changed daily to reduce infection in the neonatal unit. (Right/Wrong)	46 (92 %)	8 (16 %)
All equipment used in the neonatal intensive care unit should be sterilized. (Right/Wrong)	48 (96 %)	2 (4 %)
Cutting the nails is important in the prevention of neonatal sepsis. (Right/Wrong)	38 (76 %)	12 (24 %)
The removal of rings prevents neonatal sepsis. (Right/Wrong)	32 (64 %)	18 (36 %)
Maternal health education on the prevention of sepsis is not important in the prevention of neonatal sepsis. (Right/Wrong)	45 (90 %)	5 (10 %)
Hand washing before and after every procedure prevents sepsis. (Right/Wrong)	48 (96 %)	2 (4 %)
Minimizing invasive procedures is important for preventing neonatal sepsis. (Right/Wrong)	46 (92 %)	8 (16 %)
Active involvement of mothers in care increases neonatal sepsis. (Right/Wrong)	38 (76 %)	12 (24 %)

Table 3
Organisms causing neonatal sepsis

Organism	Frequency	Percentage
Bacteria	50	100 %
Virus	37	74 %
Fungi	24	48 %

Table 4
Knowledge of equipment commonly used in SNCU

Equipment knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
Ambu bags and masks	46	92 %
Suction machine	42	84 %
Laryngoscope	30	60 %
Endotracheal tubes of different sizes	47	94 %
Oxygen source	48	96 %
Mechanical ventilators	2	4 %
Pulse oximetry	46	92 %
Central line kit	12	24 %
Arterial line kit	4	8 %
Incubator	25	50 %

Table 5
Risk factors for neonatal sepsis

Risk factor	Frequency	Percentage
Premature rupture of membranes	23	46 %
Intrapartum maternal pyrexia and infections	27	54 %
Prematurity	41	82 %
Intrapartum handling	16	32 %
Poor hand hygiene	43	86 %

Regarding identifying signs and symptoms of neonatal sepsis, the majority had a good or satisfactory knowledge of the signs and symptoms of neonatal sepsis. For example, 90 % knew fever as a sign of neonatal sepsis, (86 %) babies not looking well, (78 %) feeding problems, (74 %) hypothermia, (74 %) lethargy. In contrast, only 50 % considered skin mottling as a sign of neonatal sepsis (Table 6).

Table 6
Identification of symptoms and signs of neonatal sepsis

Symptom/Sign	Frequency	Percentage
Fever	45	90 %
Feeding problems	39	78 %
Lethargy	37	74 %
Skin mottling	25	50 %
The baby is not looking well	43	86 %
Respiratory distress	41	82 %
RBS fluctuations	33	66 %
Hypothermia	37	74 %

4. Discussion

The results showed that 72.0 % of the nurses were of the age group of 21–30 years, consistent with T Sharmin et al. (2021) [8] and with Fayed (2016) [9], where the age was between 20 to 39 years. However, Sayed et al. [10] observed that nearly two-thirds (60 %) of the nurses were 30 to less than 40 years old, which is inconsistent with our study.

Also, all of the studied nurses were females, quite similar to (Shauq & Muala'a 2008) [11] and T Sharmin et al. (2021) [8], which revealed that most of the nurses were female.

In our study, 48 % of nurses were Muslim, and 46 % of nurses were married, similar to T Sharmin et al. (2021) [8]. In our study, 78 % of the nurses had done BSc nursing 22 % had diplomas. Sayed et al. [10] found 67 % of nurses as secondary nursing school graduates, while 24 % completed their university nursing education and only 8.6 % had technical nursing institute certification. Shinde et al. [12] found the professional education of study subjects was 90 %. Whereas Berhe et al. 2016 [13] and Obaid et al. 2015 [14], most of the nurses have a diploma or secondary school education, respectively. Most of the nurses had the experience of 2 to 4 years. This is similar to what was reported by Berhe et al., 2016 [13] study done in Ethiopia.

The study results revealed that most nurses had good knowledge of essential newborn care, consistent with a study by Ayiasi et al., 2014 [15], which showed that most nurses had good knowledge about ENC management and identifying/stabilizing LBW babies. In addition, 56.0 % of nurses were attending special courses/training in neonatology in T Sharmin et al. (2021) [8], in contrast to our study, where only 18 % have done special courses in neonatology.

Most of the nurses who participated in this study had good knowledge of most items of neonatal sepsis. These results are similar to Berhe et al., 2016 [13] and Obaid et al., 2015 [14], which showed that more than half of the nurses who participated in the study had accepted knowledge regarding neonatal sepsis. Louis et al. [16] observed initial steps of resuscitation, comprising of drying the baby, suctioning and then stimulating the baby, were also evaluated. However, all the

3 steps were known to only 16 %, while 71 % knew at least 1 of the 3 steps, and 13 % did not know any of these initial steps, in contrast to our study, where 82 % knew the initial steps of resuscitation.

Kajal et al. [17] and Louis et al. [16] observed that all the nurses knew about early initiation of breastfeeding and burping, prevention of sepsis and danger signs consistent with our study. In addition, in our study, 64 % reported removals of rings to prevent neonatal sepsis.

While all nurses had satisfactory knowledge regarding the causative organisms, all of them knew bacteria causing neonatal sepsis, whereas only 48 % knew that fungi could also cause sepsis; wider knowledge was noted among BSc-qualified groups indicating knowledge gained via case exposure and probably improved curriculum. Regarding equipment's used in SNCU, most nurses had good knowledge about basic ones, whereas less about advanced ones. Those nurses who have done special courses/training in neonatology were aware of advanced equipment's. Most of the nurses were aware of the consequences of missing signs and symptoms of neonatal sepsis. Overall knowledge turned out to be satisfactory in all the participants yet there were a few areas to which more attention should be paid.

According to the results, most nurses have a positive attitude(by counting the questions as satisfactory or not satisfactory) towards recognizing neonatal sepsis regarding answers related attitudes, similar to the study conducted by Boettiger et al. 2017 [18] and Kamunge, 2013 [19] that showed most of the nurses had strongly positive attitudes.

Study Limitation: One of the present study's main limitations is that most of the sampled healthcare workers were nurses. Therefore, generalizations about other groups of health workers should be made. Future studies may ensure the equal representation of different professional groups of healthcare workers.

Prospects for further research: More studies needs to be done in all the departments, especially ICUs and critical care areas, so that knowledge deficiencies may be bridged and patient care may be improved. Since nursing officers are the frontline assessors of newborns/sick patients, their knowledge of patient care / neonatal sepsis and early recognition play a key role in the management of this life-threatening condition. Ultimately will lead to a reduction of the global burden of morbidity and mortality.

5. Conclusion

The current study recommends the following:

- Updating knowledge of nurses through continuing in-service educational programs.
- Emphasizing the importance of the latest evidence-based practices of infection control through continuing education/training programs.
- Providing training programs for newly recruited nurses about infection control measures at regular intervals.
- Standardized nursing guidelines about infection control should be used to guide the nurses in the management of neonates with sepsis.
- Counselling services regarding prevention, detection and management of neonatal sepsis should be available in each study setting in addition to brochures, booklets, and intervention media programs containing simple information about needs and problems.
- A replication of this type of study using an observation checklist should be done to assess the level of practice.
- Furthermore, the key barriers to neonatal sepsis prevention and management were identified as poor staffing, inability to pay for services, and inadequate healthcare resources needs to be addressed.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest concerning this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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